

Research

Investigating Challenges Faced by English Language Teachers in Implementing Outcome Based Education (OBE) System in Engineering Universities of Sindh

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Abstract: Outcome Based Education (OBE) is learner-centered approach which ensures learners' learning at each stage to enable learners know what is expected to learn at the end of course. Pakistan is full signatory member of Washington Accord, Pakistan Engineering Council (PEC) has implemented OBE system in its member institutions to promote quality and meet worldwide standards of professional engineers. In this regards, this present study aims to investigate the challenges faced by English language teachers in implementing OBE model in English language courses in engineering universities of Sindh. Following qualitative approach to meet the objectives of the study 16 documents containing 80 statements were analyzed, semi-structured interviews from same 16 English language teachers were taken from whom the documents were collected. The teachers' understanding was examined through provided documents which showed inadequate understanding to implement OBE. The challenges of teachers were revealed through semi-structured interviews including assessment, evaluation, pedagogical, lack of OBE training and lack of administrative support. This study can be helpful to cope with problems faced by English language teachers who are teaching English language courses in engineering universities on OBE system.

Keywords: Outcome Based Education (OBE), English Language Teachers, English Language Courses.

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Introduction

Teaching English language on traditional language teaching methods got ample consideration and has remain under discussion for many decades. This trend has been now shifted into modern language teaching methods which emphasizes on learner-oriented and result-oriented outcomes. Previously, many studies have been conducted on implementing these traditional methods including: Grammar Translation Method (GTM), Direct Method (DM), Audiolingual Method (AM), Communicative Language Teaching Method (CLT) and Total Physical Response (TPR) but these methods are generally emphasizing on teacher-centered, textbooks, curriculum and need based approaches. Alvin Toffler, an expert of education from America says that the uneducated of the present century are not those who are not able to read and write rather those who are not able to learn, unlearn and relearn what is needed to be with respect to their needs. This educational incline towards educational system can be observed in many developed societies which does not only focuses on the what learners have learnt in actual situation but helps educators and learners to keep eye on their own continuous progress with respect to the needs of society and their own. Outcome Based Education (OBE) system keeps learners known to their outcomes which are decided prior to their learning process (Barak. M., & Hacker. M., 2012) [1].

OBE is initiative of International Engineering Alliance to promote quality among professional engineers which according to them is the need of society and the world. OBE is student-centered education system prioritizing what learners need to learn rather what teachers teach (Kamran, et al. 2020) [2]. Pakistan is full signatory member of Washington Accord which is accrediting board besides Seoul Accord, Dublin Accord Sidney Accord. Pakistan Engineering Council (PEC) is accrediting body in Pakistan for all engineering universities and Degree Awarding Institution (DIAs) which implements OBE system in engineering programs of its following members. PEC has approved twelve graduate attributes to the learners enrolled in engineering programs these attributes are reflecting not only eclectic abilities but retorting what the students will be able to learn among attitudes, skills and knowledge. OBE enables learners to achieve attributes after completing their program which are achieved specially through proper assessment (Elliott, et al. 1999)[3]. Implementing OBE in Pakistani educational institutions is not an easy task because traditional or conventional system has been deeply penetrated but the novice roadmap and framework of OBE can be a transformational. It has been implemented since Pakistan has been declared as full signatory of Washington Accord but the pace is slow. The spirit of OBE is to raise the level of learners to achieve the expected outcomes which ensures that the students are getting the dedicated attributes because it measures the learners' abilities that how they are adapting and thinking critically in solving the complex problems of the society and their own coming on the way. Tuckman (2004) [4] maintains that OBE gives the structure of curriculum to be implementing practically to assess and report the practices needed in educational institutions. It has been seen that OBE implementation depends upon teachers' understanding because without properly knowing the essence of OBE it is difficult to compete the objectives set prior. Spady (1994) [5] emphasizes that OBE is based on the constructivist method where all the learners are following their own way to construct to get information and to process that information to make the most of it because in traditional approach learners receive information passively rather OBE makes learner to get information actively. In addition, implementing OBE will be more effective if it is organized under proper supervision and training of faculty in order to get the expected outcomes in not only specific field of study but overall in learners' academic as well as professional life (Gruppen, 2012)[6].

OBE Framework

Outcome Based Education (OBE) system is based on the vision an institution holds for the progress of the society. Its epitome is vision of the institution which transfers into mission statement. The mission of the institution is further divided into three Program Educational Objectives (PEOs) reflecting the overall attributes of the program offered by

the institution which can be achieved through various subparts in specific process Geen, et al., (2009) [7]. The PEOs are mapped with mission of the program set prior followed by Program Learning Outcomes (PLOs) which are related to the aptitude, awareness and performance that the learners acquire during the program. Each PLO is driven from the curriculum designed and the content developed. There are twelve PLOs designed by Pakistan Engineering Council (PEC) which are subjected on learners' achievement by the time of their graduation. The Course Learning Outcomes (CLOs) are also designed by the experts of the course based on the content. CLOs are aligned with PLOs and PLOs are mapped with the PEOs ultimately following the mission and accomplishing the vision of the institution. These outcomes are integrated from each aspect of the program and likely to be achieved successfully by the learners when the academic program is completed (Hager, 2006) [8].

Essence of OBE

Driscoll et al., (2007) [9] state that OBE model keeps on nurturing the students learning and promotes the qualitative progress of the institution on the basis of learners' learning. Learners with respective the needs of society are trained which recognizes the knowledge-based economy with its essential educational components. It does not only trains the learners but teachers simultaneously because it leads students to successful learning which encourages teachers to be well prepared Killen (2002) [10]. Teachers understanding of OBE plays prominent role in achieving expected outcomes because clear understanding can lead students to be well prepared and can make learners find what actually they need to learn. Whatever is taught and assisted by the educator will reflect in the behavior of learners. Educators' contribution in the class is reflected in the form of learners in the society who play significant role in the progress and contribution of society. It helps learners and educators in so many ways which can be shown during the program and at the completion of the it (Kellen, 2003)[11].

Implementing OBE in English language courses

There are many courses of English language taught in various institutions which are designed according to their needs but there are limited course which are taught to engineering students. There are three non-major course taught in engineering programs of Sindh (Pathan, 2012) [12]. These courses are Functional English (FE), Communication Skills (CS) and Technical Report Writing (TRW). FE is founding course and CS course is designed to enhance the communication skills of engineers while they are during the program or at the practice. TRW is specific course in which field specific technical writings are taught so that the learners may not feel difficulty in their respective fields. Sunseri (2004) [13] maintains that the idea that all learners learn and success in parallel way which indicates that learners are trained in a way that each of them can have equal opportunity to achieve and succeed this notion seems not easy to be achieved because implementing OBE in English language courses may face different challenges like: lack of motivation, large class setting, various cultural background of learners, teachers' attitudes towards course, lack of OBE understanding and training and assessment strategies.

Research Methodology

Researchers' philosophical assumptions initiates the inquiry phenomenon to understand the nature of reality and to it ends at the emergence of the study (Creswell, et al, 2007)[14]. The present study follows qualitative approach and characteristics it follows because it involves the narrated data collection extensively in order to achieve in-depth insights of the phenomenon. In qualitative research methodology the inquiry begins from knowing the reality dimension which emerges from the nature of it to followed values till the structure of production (Turner, 2010)[15]. Qualitative research as said by Parker, L. (2004) [16] is an attempt to know and to add meanings that an individual possesses the social beliefs, notions and perceptions about the social phenomenal deeds. The qualitative strategies have been followed during the whole process inbounding the conclusions on the opinions of participants rather the numbers. Opinions about OBE on

understanding and problems faced by English language teachers were the domains of study with the interpretation of their opinions.

There were two objectives of the study. The first one was to know the understanding of English language teachers about OBE system and the second was to explore the challenges faced by English language teachers in implementing OBE system on English language course. To meet both the objectives of the study there were two sources through which the data was collected for this study. The first on knowing English language teachers' understanding was documents from English language teachers of Functional English course because this course is taught on OBE model in engineering universities of Sindh. Secondly, the interviews were conducted from same English language teachers to explore the challenges they faced while teaching this course on OBE system because asking the questions from individuals is one way to find out the process in which the interviewee is involved in practice (Tuckman, 1999)[17]. The total number of documents collected from English language teachers were ($N=16$) from four universities of Sindh including: Mehran University of Engineering and Technology, Jamshoro, NED University of Engineering and Technology, Karachi, Quaid-e-Awam University of Engineering Science and Technology, Nawabshah and Dawood University of Engineering and Technology, Karachi. Collected documents were analyzed through model of Bowen, G. A. (2009)[18]. Following the documents the interviews from 16 teachers were conducted to explore the challenges they have been facing in implementing OBE system on English language course. The fact behind conducting interviews was that interview as a tool for collecting data helps researchers to gather in-depth information about the phenomenon (Dilley, 2000) [19]. It has been observed generally that participants give preference talking over writing. Cohen, et al (2007) [20] emphasizes on that interviews are conducted to enable both interviewee and interviewer to converse and interpret the nature of world in which they are practicing their lives besides how they observe and perceive the situation with their own point of view. Interviews does not only enable researcher to know what challenges English language teachers have been facing but they also signifies the on how OBE is implemented.

Buckingham, (2015)[21] proposes three types of interviews including: structured, semi-structured and un-structured interviews. This study follows semi-structured interview because it makes the interviewer to elicit the data which appears more descriptive and probing questions are also asked while conducting the semi-structured interviews. Selecting the participants for research is essential component says Cohen, (2002) [20] because it enables the researchers to find out right participants. The purpose sampling was followed in this study to choose only those participants who are considered more relevant and interested to the study. For collecting the data ($N=04$) English language teachers were selected who have been teaching Functional English since OBE has been implemented in their universities. Selecting four participants for interviews holds a reason that it requires recording, transcribing and familiarizing of data, coding, generating themes, validating themes, defining and analyzing or interpreting and reporting is not easy says (Braun, V., & Clarke, V. 2006) [22]. These interviews were thematically analyzed by following Braun, V., & Clarke, V., model for analyzing interviews.

Results and Discussions

The objective one was to know the understanding of English language teachers about implementing OBE in Functional English language course for which the documents were collected followed by semi-structured interviews for exploring the challenges faced in implementing OBE model. The documents were analyzed into three categories. The first category was to compare the Course Learning Outcomes (CLOs) used in question papers with the CLOs approved by experts. The second category was to compare the Bloom's Taxonomy Levels used in documents with the approved. The third category was to examine if teachers have used proper Bloom's Taxonomy Verb list with respective to what they are intended to measure in the statement written in the question paper. Total number of documents analyzed were ($N=16$) each document contained five statements. Collectively there were ($N=80$) statements analyzed.

Figure 01. Shows that educators’ understanding on implementing OBE in FE course varies from each category. In the first category more than half of teachers were able to put correct CLOs while in second category the graph of correct statements used in documents is little bit more than the first category which shows that educators understanding on Bloom’s Taxonomy level was slightly more than the CLOs. The graph of third category shows that approximately one third of teachers were able to know how to use Bloom’s Taxonomy Action verb list accurately to assess what is intended to. Implementing OBE in Pakistan highlights various challenges which are not only related to institutions, stakeholders and learners but teachers as shown in figure 01.

To meet objective two which was to explore challenges faced by English language teachers in implementing OBE system in English language course for which 16 English language teachers were interviewed and analyzed through thematic analysis of Braun, V., & Clarke, V., (2006) [22] model showed that teachers have been facing five major problems related to OBE system while implementation. The challenges they faced are pedagogical, evaluation, lack of administrative support, assessment and lack of proper OBE training.

The present findings of the study reinforce Lixun’s (2011) [23] findings who states that OBE implementing not only facilitates to achieve desired outcomes but it needs proper training for teachers to implement in respective from CLOs to attaining PEOs. OBE method can have progressive results in the learners’ growth as stated by Dai et al (2017)[24] in his study resulted the similar to this present study. Mohamad (2009) [25] states that the core objective of implementing OBE is to implement the essence of it in an accurate manner.

Conclusion

PEC has approved all the institutions of Pakistan offering engineering programs for adopting OBE model under WA. In this regards, it was only option for institution to get accredited and few trainings of OBE were not sufficient to understand and implement OBE in its true spirit. However, OBE is shift from traditional educational system to modern standards which stresses on learner-centered approach rather than teacher-centered. Besides, engineering courses English language courses are also taught on OBE model. The present study investigated the challenges faced by English language teachers in implementing OBE model in English language courses following document analysis and

interviews from English language teachers from engineering universities of Sindh. The result showed that understanding of English language teachers was not sufficient to implement OBE system due to the challenges including: assessment, pedagogical, evaluation, lack of administrative support and lack of OBE training, they faced after the interviews were thematically analyzed. Thus OBE requires proper attention to implement not only on major courses of engineering program but also on English language courses because English language plays significant role not only in academic growth of engineers but in their professional career as well. This research work can be found guidance to cope with the problems faced by English language teachers to implement OBE in engineering universities.

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